

CABRISS

NEWSLETTER

Issue: 5

January 2018

www.spire2030.eu/cabriss

Welcome to the fifth newsletter of CABRISS project!

Hereby some of the (non-conventional) processes developed in the CABRISS project will be presented:

- Using recycled silicon for innovative epifoil-based heterojunction solar cells
- Recycling of Si from diamond saw wafering produced kerf
- Innovative process of Si ingot preparation by thermal spraying and hot pressing of recycled Si
- Expanding the recycling abilities of LOSER

CABRISS - Implementation of a Circular economy Based on Recycled, reused and recovered Indium, Silicon and Silver materials for photovoltaic and other applications

H2020-WASTE-2014

Starting date: June 1st, 2015

Project duration: 36 months

Coordinator: CEA-INES

Contact point: David Pelletier

+33(0)-632-218-691

+33(0)-479-792-061

E-mail: david.pelletier@cea.fr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No. 641972.

HORIZON 2020

Impact

Using Recycled Si for Innovative Epifoil-based Heterojunction Solar Cells

As PV production ramps up and numerous installed solar panels reach their end of life, potentially huge waste sources of silicon become available. Such silicon can be recovered and recycled back into the PV industry, for making solar cells directly on the recycled Si. In cases where the recycled Si is of very low purity and cannot be used directly as active material, they can instead be used to make low-cost Si supporting carriers that are highly-conductive. These supporting substrates can be fabricated using low-cost techniques such as by sintering and spraying of low-cost Si powders, developed by SINTEF and Pyrogenesis. These conductive substrates can act as mechanical carriers of thin silicon (< 50 μm) and as rear-contacts in what is called a wafer-equivalent concept.

In this work, thin epitaxial silicon foils from the imec's porous silicon-based lift-off process are used. For conductive bonding, low-temperature Ag paste from INKRON (IPC-114) has been preferably used due to its robust bonding properties (low temperature curing, high conductivity and minimal volume change). As a first demonstrative step, thin (<50 μm) epifoil-based and thinned (<50 μm) Cz-based cells conductively bonded onto highly-doped p+ Cz silicon substrates have been fabricated. We chose the heterojunction technology for cell fabrication, leading to 15.7% efficiency for the best epifoil cell and 17.9% for the best thin Cz cell, partially processed after conductive bonding. It was observed that the cell performance of bonded cells are comparable to that of non-bonded epifoil cells that were processed freestanding. Furthermore, in order to reduce costs of the conductive bonding step, extensive simulations have been performed by TU Vienna to understand the best configuration and pattern geometry for the bonding layer.

This work is done in framework of H2020 EU project CABRISS and was presented at the European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition (EUPVSEC) 2017. The paper was mentioned as one of the highlights of the conference.

Recycling of Si from diamond saw wafering produced kerf

The process of cutting silicon ingots into wafers suitable for solar cells has a Si kerf loss of approximately 40% by weight. There is progress to reduce thickness of diamond wire, which will reduce the kerf loss. Recycling of Si-kerf is energy efficient, since considerable amounts of energy have been consumed to produce PV quality silicon. Resitec estimates its process to give an energy saving of >15MWh per 1000kg Si-kerf compared to conventional production of similar Si-powder.

Diamond wire cutting is used normally with water as cutting fluid with the addition of a coolant additive. Several types of additives are available commercially and there are recommendations from the producers of the cutting equipment. CEA has investigated different types of additives and their effect on oxidation of the kerf. It is important to avoid oxidation of the kerf as much as possible during recycling to keep its quality high. Therefore, reliable passivation methods have been developed and tested in pilot and industrial scale.

Si-kerf has been recycled from diamond wire wafering and block cutting. CEA has studied recycling of Si-kerf from a conventional process and from an optimized process and achieved a high purity Si powder. This is material recycled in pilot scale from a standard industrial type diamond wire wafering saw.

The process shows a significant reduction in carbon, oxygen and metallic elements, particularly aluminum. Resitec has aimed to have a cost efficient process to produce a cheap substrate which is used further in the CABRISS project or to produce silicon powder with purity suitable as feedstock for further purification steps for PV use. Purity of 99.5-99.9% have been achieved in industrial scale and 4N purity in pilot scale.

FerroPem and Silicio FerroSolar have used the recycled material for melting and solidification with good yield and have shown further purification in melted stage. Further up-scaling tests are in progress. Recycled silicon kerf has been used in conventional and novel solar cell concepts within the CABRISS project.

Left) Results of recycled Si-kerf from a block cutting process and dry Si powder.

Right) Si chunks from melted and solidified material with its origin in Si-kerf.

Si Wafer Manufacturing by Thermal Spray and Hot Pressing of Recycled Si Powders

In the framework of the H2020 CABRISS project, Thermal Spraying and Hot Pressing technologies were applied for the manufacturing of Si wafers from recycled Si.

The process of thermal spraying involves feeding a powder based feedstock into a high-energy plasma or flame jet, in which powder particles are heated, partly or fully melted, and simultaneously accelerated, towards the target surface of a substrate. Silicon particles cool and then solidify onto the substrate, forming a re-crystallized silicon layer. Silicon powders with particle sizes in the range of about 10-50 μm were fabricated by conventional ball milling from two different Si feedstock: (i) Si kerf produced during sawing of Si wafers from the ingots, and (ii) Si powder from Si scrap (broken wafers).

It was demonstrated that Si powder based structures – free-standing Si wafers or thin Si films can be processed by thermal spray. Important to note that thin Si layers can be deposited on several types of low-cost substrates (Al, glass, Si) with the low temperature melting points. It is shown, that thermal spray processing conditions and the origin of the supporting substrates play an important role for the crystallinity of the thermal spray deposited Si layers.

It is established that fabricated at appropriate thermal spray processing conditions, such layers are poly-crystalline with a low fraction of the amorphous phase and can be considered as a low-cost alternative for Si PV, which is based on utilization of Si wafers and thin Si layers deposited by conventional methods such as CVD, PECVD, e-beam, etc.

Wafers from processed by thermal spray

The process of hot pressing is developed by RHP. Raw materials obtained from recycling of PV modules have been purified and milled by the project partner Resitec into suitable powders. This powder was further modified in order to modify the electrical properties of the ingot. Following to this a high temperature process pressure assisted sintering technique was applied to convert the powder into a solid ingot. Major challenges have been found in the identification of suitable tool materials as well protection material. Starting with small sized ingots these problems could be solved and finally it was possible to upscale the process for manufacturing of ingots with a size of 156 mm x 156 mm. In a next step these ingots have been forwarded to the project partner THM where the ingots will be sliced followed by further investigation, characterisation and fabrication of PV cells at the project partner Sintef.

Hot-pressed pseudo-square ingot with size of 156 mm x 156 mm

Expanding the recycling abilities of LOSER

The CABRISS partner LOSER has invested in November 2017 to continue and expand the recycling activities of SolarWorld at the former site in Freiberg, Saxony (Germany). The competence for recycling and reuse of silicon built up by the SolarWorld recycling team will not only be further deployed but will be directly linked to the delamination technologies for end-of-life PV modules that have been developed by LOSER in the frame of the CABRISS project. Recovered silicon can be mechanically processed (sawing, blasting, crushing and milling) and reused in different ways. The available processes involve production and reprocessing of silicon targets, recrystallization and thermal treatment of ingots for solar and non-solar applications, as well as etching and cleaning of materials in various shapes and sizes. The service is completed by electrical characterization and analysis of trace elements.

For CABRISS, this means that the targeted zero-waste and PV Circular Economy have come another step closer to a long-term exploitation by business activities of the project's individual and collaborating company partners. The name chosen for the new company is Freiburger Recycling and Silicium Technologie GmbH, in short FReSiTec.

NEWS – Events

- **CABRISS at 33rd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition (EU PVSEC),** Amsterdam, the Netherlands, 25-29 September 2017.

The following presentations were given by the consortium, and they are available in the EU PVSEC proceedings:

1. H. Sivaramakrishnan Radhakrishnan, N. Bednar, T. Bearda, R. Roozeman, J. Heikkinen, N. Adamovic, A. Ulyashin, M. Syvertsen, I. Gordon, "Solar Cells on < 50µm Thick Epitaxial Foils Conductively Bonded to Low-Cost Si Carrier", EU PVSEC Proceedings, 2017, 431 - 436 (DOI: 10.4229/EUPVSEC20172017-2CO.12.2)
2. R. Thomas, D. Pelletier, M.-C. Hoffmann, J.P. Rakotoniaina, L. Federzoni, "Cabris: Market Analysis and Business Models for a Circular Economy in PV", EU PVSEC 2017, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 25-29 September 2017

3. W. Palitzsch, "Implementation of a Circular Economy Based on Recycled, Reused and Recovered Indium, Silicon and Silver Materials for Photovoltaic and Other Applications", EU PVSEC 2017, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 25-29 September 2017
 4. M. Syvertsen, T. Halvorsen, K. Mork, A. Nordmark, T. Kaden, A. Ulyashin, "Remelting and Purification of Si-Kerf for PV-Wafers", EU PVSEC Proceedings, 2017, 1882 - 1885 (DOI: 10.4229/EUPVSEC20172017-5DV.3.71)
 5. T. Halvorsen, M. Moen, K. Mork, D. Grosset-Bourbange, P. Rivat, H. Hajjaji, V. Brizé, F. Coustier, "CABRISS: Recycling of Si-Kerf from PV", EU PVSEC Proceedings, 2017, 1524 - 1527 (DOI: 10.4229/EUPVSEC20172017-5EO.1.5)
 6. A. Derbouz Draoua, B. Martel, S. Dubois, C. Audoin, M. Serasset, A. Fauveau, H. S. Radhakrishnan, J. Denafas, L. Petreniene, N. Severino, N. Bednar, A.G. Ulyashin, "On The Fabrication Of Solar Cells Based On Newly Produced Recycled Silicon Feedstocks From CABRISS – A Comparative Study Between Material Properties And Solar Cells Performances", EU PVSEC Proceedings, 2017, 483 - 487 (DOI: 10.4229/EUPVSEC20172017-2AV.1.3)
 7. M. Vardavoulias, A.S. Azar, T. Halvorsen, M. Moen, K. Mork, P.A. Carvalho, O. Dahl, A. Ulyashin, "Si Wafer Manufacturing by Thermal Spray of Recycled Si Powders", EU PVSEC Proceedings, 2017, 509 - 512 (DOI: 10.4229/EUPVSEC20172017-2AV.1.18)
 8. T. Kaden, A.S. Azar, M. Syvertsen, H.J. Möller, N. Abrosimov, M. Fleissner Sunding, J. Hennicke, A. Ulyashin, "Silicon Powder Based Ingots and Substrates, Processed by Spark Plasma Sintering", EU PVSEC Proceedings, 2017, 513 - 516 (DOI: 10.4229/EUPVSEC20172017-2AV.1.19)
- CABRISS and Eco-Solar project consortia organized **the first CABRISS Open Workshop**, which was held on 8th June 2017, Freiberg (Germany) during the Freiberg Silicon Days. The present recent results on the topic of "Recycling, reuse and resource efficiency: New solutions for a PV circular economy" can be found on the [CABRISS website](#) (under Publications tab).
 - CABRISS M30 consortium meeting was held on 5-6 December at the partnering company Sunplugged in Innsbruck, Austria.

CABRISS

CABRISS Consortium

	www.resitec.no		
	www.tuwien.ac.at		
	www.sunplugged.at		
	www.thm.fraunhofer.de		
	www.projektkompetenz.eu		
	www.pvcycle.org		
	www.inkron.com		
	www.ecm-greentech.com		

Stay updated with CABRISS latest news and follow us

follow us on
twitter

LinkedIn